

DIRECTIONAL DIFFUSION OF MOISTURE IN CARBON FIBRE / EPOXY COMPOSITES: EXPERIMENTS AND MODELLING

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ABSTRACT

Water diffusion into composites in different directions was examined in this study, with the aim of determining the best way of measuring diffusion coefficients and also to provide values to compare with model predictions. The water absorption behaviour of unreinforced epoxy resins and carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composite materials was examined with long term exposure to different environmental conditions. Initial Fickian absorption was observed followed by a slower second stage that continues for at least 3.7 years. Fibre architecture was found to be an important aspect controlling absorption, where water diffusion along fibres was observed to be about three times faster than across the fibres and about seven times faster than through the thickness. A three-dimensional finite element computer model based on Fickian diffusion behaviour was developed to predict the levels of moisture absorption under hot/humid environments. A multi-scale modelling approach was used which allows the results of simulations at the microstructural level to be used to predict the diffusivities in different directions. Experimental results provided a baseline for the validation of the model, and comparison of these data with model predictions showed close matching and good agreement. The diffusion showed high dependency on the detailed microstructure.

1 INTRODUCTION

Today's ever increasing demand for lighter materials with higher strength, greater stiffness, and better reliability has led to extensive research on and development of composite materials. Structural composites are usually exposed to a range of environmental conditions through their service life leading to plasticisation of the resin and reductions in some properties. In hot/wet environments, there is still uncertainty of long term stability of composites, in which moisture can diffuse easily and rapidly into polymers in early stages and then increase slowly in the second stage until finally moisture reaches an equilibrium concentration and thus material saturates. A Fickian diffusion process, in which saturation reaches constant values, has been commonly used in most methods to account for the rate of moisture absorption. Conversely, a slow steady increase in moisture content beyond the initial Fickian period in epoxy composites have been reported in many studies [1-5]. An important aspect that can affect the diffusion mechanism is the fibre architecture, as it has been reported by many researchers that water access along fibres is faster than across fibres [6-8]. This is essential to consider where edge surfaces are exposed to moisture. Therefore, the determination of the mechanisms of water diffusion and the detailed modelling of water uptake can allow more modified design.

This work aimed to investigate the directional diffusion in unidirectional carbon fibre/epoxy composites, derive the directional diffusivity from measured data using different methods to account for edge effects, and finally model and validate a detailed UD composite structure. The experimental curves and diffusivity ratios were compared with predictions from FE modelling at two scales based on the detailed microstructure.

2 MATERIALS AND CONDITIONING

Composite samples comprising T800S Carbon fibres and M21 epoxy resin were manufactured into unidirectional lay-up sheets generally of 25 mm thickness (132 plies) using conventional autoclave processing. The composite panels passed ultrasonic inspection and volume fraction measurements showed them to have a V_f of 58% with a void content of less than 0.2%. In order to understand the effects of fibre orientations and arrangements on diffusion, these UD sheets were cut into samples with various thicknesses in three different orientations: along the fibres, across the layers and through the thickness which are shown in (Fig.1) as 1, 2 and 3 respectively. The specimens needed to be relatively thin so that diffusion into the specimen was mainly through the largest surfaces and to ensure that diffusion through the smaller surfaces was negligible, hence reducing the ‘edge effects’. Specimens with various thicknesses were used to examine the edge effects and thickness effects on the diffusion rate.

Figure 1: UD orientations

Samples were prepared from these sheets by water-jet cutting into blocks followed by accurate sectioning with a metallographic diamond saw. Sets of samples were cut with the thin dimension parallel to the x, y or z direction which represent 1, 2 and 3 directions respectively. All samples were approximately 25mm x 25mm in size with a thickness of 1, 2 or 4mm. A total of 90 separate samples were cut, where two samples of each thickness in each of the three orientations were tested in five moisture absorption conditions. Cut surfaces of samples were investigated under optical and SEM microscopes which showed no observable damage due to either the water-jet cutting or diamond saw sectioning. Unreinforced resin samples of the same material were supplied by the materials manufacturer with dimensions of 33mm x 19.9mm x 4mm.

3 DIRECTIONAL DIFFUSION OF WATER INTO COMPOSITES

It is well established that the rate of diffusion can be very dependent on direction in fibre-composites [6-12]. This can be due to the anisotropic nature of most carbon fibre composites which may lead to anisotropic water diffusion behaviour. Generally, if the thickness of the composite is not small compared to the other dimensions then moisture entering through the edges has to be taken into account if the edges do not have a moisture-impermeable coating. Diffusion in general is fast along the fibres with slower diffusion through the thickness of the composite which can be down to straighter

and shorter diffusion paths, and also due to debonding along the fibres or interphase effects. Therefore, during design, directional diffusion needs to be considered if water absorption is measured, either by direct measurement or by modelling. [9]

(Table 1) summarises some of the previous studies that have considered this effect using various materials and fibre arrangements and using various methods to measure the directional diffusion behaviour, where all methods measure water uptake in certain directions and monitor weight changes during conditioning. These studies show that the ratio of longitudinal to transverse diffusion coefficient has been measured as anything between 2 and 24. Being able to measure these different diffusion rates is important for any modelling of water uptake, and while there will be some differences from material to material, a robust method of measuring the difference is needed.

Author(s)	Material	Direction	M_{∞} %	D ($\times 10^{-14}$ m ² /s)
Leung et al (1979)[10]	AS/3501-5 graphite/epoxy composites	Along Across Through	-	162 68 63
Arao et al (2007) [11]	UD CF/EP	Along Across Through	1.3	154 68 36
Aoki et al (2008) [12]	T800H/3633 carbon fibre/epoxy laminates	Fibre direction Transverse direction	1.73-1.74	803 32.5

Table 1: Directional diffusion constants of carbon fibre/epoxy resin composites from previous studies

Initially, in this study attempts were made to seal up the edges of composite samples, using adhesive-backed foil tape and vacuum-deposited thin layers of aluminium. In all cases, some water was found to penetrate the sealed material and so these methods could not be used reliably. Therefore, as it was felt that edge effects would be important, specimens of different thickness with directions along the fibres, across the layers or through the thickness were tested to determine the directional diffusion coefficients.

3.1 CONDITIONING AND MEASUREMENTS

Specimens were first dried in an oven at 70 °C until the specimen weights were stabilized before conducting the absorption experiments. All unidirectional and resin specimens were conditioned in water at 23, 40 and 70 °C, and also in 45%, 60% and 85 % RH at 70 °C. The weight gain of the specimens was carefully monitored by weighing them periodically at increasing intervals using a balance with a resolution of 0.01 mg. and the percentage weight gain, $W\%$, was determined.

The weight gain of each sample was plotted against the square root of time with the expectation that the samples would show Fickian behaviour and so the first part of this graph would be linear. (Fig.2) (right) shows the effect of direction for 2mm thick samples conditioned in 70°C water. (Fig.2) (left) shows the effect of sample thickness for the through-thickness samples for the same condition. These graphs show features that are not too surprising. The thicker samples have a slower weight

uptake, and the samples with the thin dimension along the fibres have a faster uptake than those cut across the fibres which is faster than those cut through the layers.

Figure 2: Water uptake curves through the thickness of CF/M-21 specimens in water at 70 °C (left).

Water uptake curves for different orientations CF/M-21 specimens with 2mm thickness in water at 70 °C (right)

3.2 PARAMETERS ESTIMATION TECHNIQUE FOR FICKIAN DIFFUSION BEHAVIOUR

Conventional Fickian diffusion curves generally level-off near the transition point at which the slope of the curve changes, and corresponds to constant moisture content beyond this transition point [13]. However, for neat resin and the composites, even after more than 4 years of exposure, equilibrium has not been reached clearly. The FE model used in this study deals only with Fickian diffusion, so that it was necessary to extract the Fickian component of the curve. Therefore, since M_∞ is necessary for the calculation of the diffusion coefficients and in order to model the Fickian diffusion, it was important to determine the moisture level (M_f) at which the best curve fit for the Fickian part can be obtained. For these, the long term behaviour for resin and composites under all conditions could be subtracted, giving a value of the Fickian saturation for each sample, as illustrated in (Fig.3). It has to be mentioned that increasing the thickness of the specimen increases the time needed for the specimens to saturate (into the slow second-stage behaviour). As a result of that, some specimens were still absorbing water in the Fickian stage and no sign of the second stage was noticed. This would mean that D values for these specimens couldn't be obtained. It was seen, however, that the saturation level was quite similar for those samples that did reach the second-stage, regardless of sample direction and thickness. The variations in the moisture content of specimens in different directions that were seen may be due to the variation in the resin volume fraction of the specimens.

For thicker samples in different directions, and those conditioned at lower temperature, it was not possible to get a good extrapolation of the long-term behaviour within reasonable test duration. It can be assumed that the Fickian saturation is the same at each condition, regardless of sample thickness or orientation. However it was found that there was variation in V_f from sample to sample, due to the complex microstructure and relatively small sample size, and this would cause variations in the Fickian saturation for each sample. For samples that had not saturated, the following method was used. In an attempt to handle any differences in fibre volume fraction between samples, the measured Fickian saturation values were used for all samples that did saturate. For samples that did not saturate,

the average saturation values for that condition were used, but scaled by sample density as an approximate measure of the fibre volume fraction. The measured values of saturated samples and then average values scaled by density of unsaturated samples were used. The same fitting method was used for resin samples to deduce saturation at all conditions. The saturation values for resin and composite specimens are given in (Table 2).

Figure 3: Extraction of Fickian behaviour from long term water uptake measurements

3.3 DIFFUSION COEFFICIENT

The moisture absorption as a function of time is given by the three-dimensional Fickian model, Equation (1):

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = D_x \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} + D_y \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} + D_z \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial z^2} \quad (1)$$

Where C is the concentration, t the time and D_x , D_y and D_z are the diffusion coefficients.

For an infinite thin plate, the approximation for initial uptake or short term diffusion (up to about $M_t/M_\infty = 0.6$), is given by equation 2:

$$\frac{M_t}{M_\infty} = \frac{4}{h} \sqrt{\frac{tD}{\pi}} \quad (2)$$

Where M_t is the absorption at time t , M_∞ is the saturation and h is the plate thickness.

In composites, the fibres can act as a barrier to the absorbed water molecules, so when the diffusion is perpendicular to the fibres the diffusion path will be more complicated than when the diffusion is along the fibres and the diffusion behaviour will be more complicated. To consider this directional diffusion behaviour and to account for diffusion from edges, four different methods were compared:

- Extrapolation to zero thickness (Intercept)
- Using correction factor, Equation (3), derived by Shen and Springer [14] and extended to the case of anisotropic diffusion by Bao and Yee [15].

$$f_{ss} = \left(1 + \frac{h}{l} \sqrt{\frac{D_y}{D_x}} + \frac{h}{w} \sqrt{\frac{D_z}{D_x}} \right) \quad (3)$$

- Using another alternative approximation developed by Starink, Starink and Chambers [16], Equation (4).

$$f_{ssc} = 1 + 0.54 \frac{h}{l} \sqrt{\frac{D_y}{D_x}} + 0.54 \frac{h}{w} \sqrt{\frac{D_z}{D_x}} + 0.33 \frac{h^2}{l.w} \sqrt{\frac{D_z D_y}{D_x^2}} \quad (4)$$

- The full 3-D solution to the Fickian equation with anisotropic diffusion coefficients, Equation (5). [17]

$$G_{3D} = \frac{M_t}{M_\infty} = \left[1 - \left(\frac{8}{\pi^2} \right)^3 \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{((2i+1)(2j+1)(2k+1))^2} \exp \left[-\pi^2 t \left[D_x \left(\frac{2i+1}{L} \right)^2 + D_y \left(\frac{2j+1}{l} \right)^2 + D_z \left(\frac{2k+1}{e} \right)^2 \right] \right] \right] \quad (5)$$

Detailed explanation of using these approximation methods can be found in other papers [9, 22] which concluded that the use of the Starink, Starink and Chambers (SSC) model is in close agreement with the full 3-D one. The Shen and Springer (S&S) approximation was shown to give systematically low values for diffusion across and through the fibres because it considers diffusion from all faces of a rectangular block, but does not take account of diffusion at edges or corners. The full 3-D analysis of diffusion is normally a time consuming computation, so the SSC method for determining the diffusivity for all conditions was used. It was clear that the key part to this is really good experimental data and the use of repeat samples to average any differences in V_f and fibre geometry between samples. The diffusivity was noticed to vary with fibre orientation, where there is definitely lower diffusion through thickness than along layers. Resin diffusivity (D_r) was obtained assuming that diffusion is the same in all directions. The saturation and diffusivity values for resin and composite specimens were determined to be used for the modelling and shown in (Table 2). D_x was assumed to be the same as D_r .

Condition	Saturation, weight %		Diffusion coefficients ,		
	M_∞ %		$\times 10^{-14}$ m ² /sec		
	Epoxy	Composite	$D_x=D_r$	D_y	D_z
23°C in water	3.7	1.36	12.1	4.8	2.3
40°C in water	3.8	1.35	32.0	13.1	5.0
70°C in water	3.95	1.34	141.4	71.9	22.6
70°C, 45% RH	0.7	0.35	186	91.9	32.6
70°C, 60% RH	1.1	0.6	185	70.8	25.8
70°C, 85% RH	2.4	1.08	159	70.8	24.2

Table 2: Experimental directional diffusivities and saturation values of M21 UD samples at various conditions

4 MODELLING OF DIRECTIONAL DIFFUSION IN COMPOSITES

Directional diffusion coefficients can also be derived by fitting experimental weight uptake curves to either the full 3-D Fickian solution [16] or to FE models of 3-D diffusion [13,17]. The effective diffusivity in composites with impermeable fibres has been examined by many researchers by using 3D finite element analysis on a fibre matrix unit cell [1, 18-20, 23]. The aim in this section was to

develop a finite element model to predict the Fickian diffusion of water into unidirectional carbon fibre/epoxy composites with varying temperatures and humidity.

4.1 MULTI-SCALE STRUCTURE

For modelling purposes, optical microscopy was used to identify the composite structure. The optical microscope images of these materials, (Fig.4) (left), showed only yarns (tows) of fibre-rich regions with very high volume fraction embedded in epoxy resin. The yarns were measured to be about 225 μm thick, and the resin layers between them approximately 10% of that. The average fibre diameter was 5.7 μm . Fibre volume fraction (V_f) within the yarns was measured by counting the number of fibres in three representative fibre-rich areas and calculating the corresponding area and hence volume fraction. This gave $V_f = 75\%$ for these regions. The yarns have been observed from the images to be not continuous, but the resin-rich layers are continuous and they have a thickness of 10% of the fibre-rich plies. Due to the difference in the architecture of these composites, the success of the finite element model depends on how realistically the geometry of the sample architecture is modelled and how well the effective properties of the different fibre regions are determined. It has been found that at the level of individual fibres, the predicted diffusivity of a unit cell depends significantly on the fibre volume fraction and arrangement, which have an effect on the gap size between fibres and the path length of diffusion through the matrix. Modelling using a regular fibre distribution has been found to give higher diffusivity than a random fibre distribution which has smaller gaps and longer diffusion paths [23]. Random distribution of fibres has been found to give results closer to measured data [19, 21]; therefore fibres in the design step were randomly distributed.

Figure 4: Cross section of UD composite (a) 20x magnification showing fibre-rich regions separated by resin layers, and (b) 800x magnification of a fibre-rich region (left). UD CF/M21 composite structures at two scales modelling (right)

4.2 COMPOSITE DIFFUSIVITY PREDICTION

The first stage of the modelling was to predict the three directional diffusion coefficients. The fibres were assumed to be parallel in the x-direction, so that D_x was assumed to be the same as that for the resin. 2D modelling could then be carried out in the y-z plane only. The second stage was to carry out 3D modelling to predict the water uptake curve for a “real” sample.

Due to this complicated structure of these materials, the modelling was performed at three scales. At the microscale, circular fibres were randomly placed within a square unit cell. At the mesoscale,

TexGen (a textile modelling package) was used for designing the geometry of the yarn structure [24]. For the whole composite sample, simple box geometry applied.

At all scales, Hypermesh (a finite element analysis package) was used to mesh the structure with triangular or tetrahedral elements because these can more accurately represent the geometry between closely packed fibres and yarns [25]. (Fig.4) (right) shows the micro- and meso- scales designed and FE meshed according to the first two steps. Finally, the outputs from the above packages were combined with an in-house modelling program for liquid diffusion. The computer model used to predict moisture diffusion was a Finite Element code based on the Fickian diffusion model and written in FORTRAN 95, which could run in either 2D or 3D using 3- or 4- node elements based on the methods described in Smith and Griffiths [26]. The model equations and boundary conditions are detailed below:

- **Saturation Equation**

Equation (6) was applied to calculate the saturation moisture content M_{∞} (kg/m³) for the designed structure depending on the fibre volume fraction.

$$M_{\infty} = (1-V_f)M_{\infty,epoxy} + V_f M_{\infty,fibre/yarn} \quad (6)$$

In the case of micro-scale, i.e. fibres and resin within a yarn, V_f is the volume fraction of fibres within the yarn, and since the carbon fibres don't absorb any water, $M_{\infty,fibre}=0$. At the meso-scale, i.e. yarns within the composite, v_f is the volume fraction of yarns within the composite and $M_{\infty,yarn}$ is the saturation moisture content within a yarn.

- **Diffusion Equation**

Equation (7) was implemented using [P] the three dimensional permeability tensor = M_{∞} [D] (kg/m/sec) [20, 21, 23]. The continuous relative concentration $C^* = C/M_{\infty}$ was used to address the complexity at material boundaries, between yarns and resin, where the concentration is discontinuous.

$$\nabla^T [P] \nabla C^* - \frac{\partial}{\partial t} C^* = 0 \quad (7)$$

Solving the finite element representation of this equation was carried out using a pre-conditioned conjugate gradient method. [22]

- **Boundary Conditions**

- 1- The geometry and nodes of each face were forced to be identical to those on the opposite face without the need for the internal cells to be symmetrical. This enabled the modelling of a semi-infinite plate.
- 2- At the first two scales to predict the directional diffusion coefficients:
 - 2.1. For diffusion in the one- direction, boundary conditions were applied to mimic an infinite plate in the other two directions. For example, if diffusion is in z-direction then the relative concentration at each node on the minimum "y" face was forced to be equal to that at the node directly opposite on the maximum "y" face.
 - 2.2. Steady state diffusion through the sample was modelled by setting the concentration on the ingoing and outgoing faces at saturation and zero respectively.
 - 2.3. At steady state, an effective diffusivity D_{eff} was calculated using Fick's first law to the sample as a whole and to individual elements, from Equation (8).

$$D_{eff} = \left(\frac{h}{M_\infty} \right) \langle [P] \{ \nabla C^* \} \cdot \{ n \} \rangle \quad (8)$$

{n} is the vector in the diffusion direction, and <> signifies a volume average. This averages the flux over all elements and so takes account of in-homogeneity in the sample. [22]

3- For modelling the whole sample, a one-eighth size box was used with saturation concentration on three orthogonal faces and a reflective boundary condition on each opposite face.

4.3 MODELLING RESULTS AND VALIDATION

In order to validate the accuracy of the model, diffusion coefficients and equilibrium moisture content derived from the water absorption experiments on the unfilled resin were fed into the model, and then comparison of the predicted and measured water uptake curves for the composite and comparison of predicted and measured diffusivity in the y, and z-directions were carried out. Firstly, the value $D_{yz1,pred}$ was obtained from a unit cell with individual fibres representative of the fibre-rich regions of the composite, with a typical V_f of 0.75. Since the micrographs showed no obvious difference between the y- and z- directions, a single diffusion coefficient could be used in this case. This is shown in (Fig.5)(right) which gives both rich-fibre structure and whole composite structure with colours indicating the concentration profile at steady state when diffusion was in the y- and z- directions. Fibre-rich yarns, with $D_x=D_r$, $D_y=D_z=D_{yz1}$ were then embedded in resin in a structure representative of the whole composite, as shown in (Fig.5)(left). This also shows the concentration profile for diffusion in the y- and z-direction at steady state. Diffusivities D_y and D_z were calculated. For the Fickian diffusion modelled, the predicted ratios D_y/D_r and D_z/D_r were determined by the unit cell geometries so were the same for all conditions. Measured values were then compared with these ratios, (Fig.5) (left). It can be seen that a close match to the average was achieved.

Figure 5: Comparison of predicted ratios D_y/D_r and D_z/D_r with measured values for the UD CF/M21 composite(left). a) Fibre / resin arrangement representing rich-fibre regions in UD composite structure (b) represents the overall UD M21 composite structure(right). All figures have a concentration profile for y- and z-direction diffusion at steady state

Finally the moisture uptake curve for the whole sample was predicted. (Fig.6) shows the comparison between the experimental and the predicted weight uptake curves. The graphs show a close match between the measured and predicted curves. The predicted curves also showed that longer time is needed to reach saturation in the case of diffusion through the thickness which may be attributed to the complex diffusion path where water has to go around the fibre compared to the diffusion along the fibre where the diffusion path is straight forward.

Figure 6: Comparison of predicted and measured water uptake curves for specimens (2mm thickness) conditioned at 70 °C / water across the fibres(left) and through the layers (right)

5 CONCLUSION

Water diffusion measurements of composites with different orientations show that the diffusivity across fibres and through the thickness was found to be smaller than along the fibres by factors of about 2-3 and 3-7, respectively. This can be attributed primarily to longer and more complicated diffusion paths across fibres and through the thickness of fibres. It was found separation of Fickian behaviour, scaling by sample density as an approximate measure of the fibre volume fraction for obtaining saturation and using the Starink, Starink and Chambers edge correction factor for deriving diffusivity are the best combination of methods to determine the saturation values and diffusivity needed for modelling. It has been also found that multi-scale modelling starting from the behaviour at the level of individual fibres followed by larger scale models can be used accurately to derive the diffusion properties of representative unit cells. The accurate representation of the detailed microstructure is the critical factor to matching the predicted diffusivities with the measured data. Validation of model predictions against experimental results was found to give close matching for diffusivities and moisture absorption behaviour in composites with various environmental conditions.

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